

Synthesis and antimicrobial screening of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets

Raksha S. Bokade* and Gajanan V. Korpe

P.G. Department of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 003, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : rakshadaware@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Starting from acetylated lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide and aryl isocyanates herein we describe a synthetic methodology for the preparation of a wide range of various isothiobiurets. This converted high isolated yields which can find application in the area of medicinal chemistry. The identities of these newly synthesized compounds are established on the basis of elemental analysis IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and Mass spectral analysis. These compounds were assayed for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against some selected pathogenic organisms like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *Ps. aeruginosa*, *P. vulgaris*, *B. cereus* and *A. niger*, *C. albicans* to get potent bioactive molecule.

Keywords : Lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide, aryl isocyanates, isothiobiurets, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Carbohydrates play an important role in vast array of biological processes and particularly there are many advantages¹. The use of carbohydrates as organic raw materials is attractive since some of them are readily available renewable commodities². Literature survey reveals various pharmacological important applications such as anti-inflammatory, antitumor, hypnotic activities due to which there is high interest in synthesizing various sugar thiobiurets. There is a growing need for new class of antibacterial compounds having different mechanism of action compared to existing drugs. Carbohydrate containing *S*-benzyl isothioureas enhance the antimicrobial activity of that compound³. Thiobiurets (mono and di) are important derivatives of thiourea which may increase the biological activity of thioureas. The mono and dithiobiuret derivatives are effective fungicides, bacteriocides, herbicides and also have demonstrated effective growth regulating activity⁴. Some thiobiuret derivatives also showed analgesic⁵, anticonvulsant and hypnotic activity⁶⁻⁸. Many of the substituted thioureas are active as anti HIV⁹, antiviral¹⁰, antimicrobial¹¹, antitubercular¹², antitumor¹³, antihypertensive¹⁴ and anticarcinogenic agents¹⁵. Because of biological importance carbohydrate have aroused much interest in synthetic and medicinal chemistry¹⁶.

Thus, considerable efforts have been devoted to the synthesis of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets.

Results and discussion

Thus the synthesized novel hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-aryl-2-*S*-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets exhibits comparable antibacterial and antifungal activities against the organism tested. The method adopted in the synthesis and investigation is simple, efficient and inexpensive in synthesizing pharmacologically important molecules.

Experimental

Melting points of the synthesized compounds were recorded on electro thermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Specific rotations of the newly synthesized compounds were measured on Equip-Tronic digital polarimeter model no. EQ 801 at 30 °C in CHCl_3 . IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrophotometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as an internal reference. The MS spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX-102 FAB mass spectrophotometer and ^{13}C NMR were recorded in CDCl_3 . Purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography using Merck silica gel coated aluminum plates and

petroleum ether : ethylacetate as eluent. The synthetic strategy involved the interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide with aryl isocyanates. All solvents were freshly distilled before use.

Synthesis of hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide :

The required hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide is prepared by earlier known method¹⁷ by interaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl thiocarbamide with benzyl chloride in ethanolic medium. The various aryl isocyanates were received from Sigma-Aldrich company.

1-Hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-o-tolyl-2-S-benzyl-2-isothiobiurets (3a) :

1-Hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-*o*-tolyl-2-*S*-benzyl-isothiobiuret (**3a**) was synthesized by mixing solution of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide (0.005 *M*, 3.92 g, 10 ml benzene) (**1**) with aryl isocyanates (0.005 *M*, 0.66 ml) (**2a-i**) in dry benzene medium and stirring at room temperature for 24 h while monitoring the reaction by TLC. Benzene was distilled off and the resultant syrupy mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), to afford white granular solid (**3a**) crystallized from ethanol. The characterization of product (**3a**) was established by IR¹⁸, ¹H NMR^{19–23}, ¹³C NMR and Mass²⁴ spectral studies.

1-Hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-o-tolyl-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3a) :

IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3423 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.), 1749 (C=O str.), 1508 (C=N str.), 1407 (C-N), 669 (C=S str.), 924 (char. of lactose unit), 758 (*ortho* substituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 7.375–7.014 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 5.534–3.603 (16H, m, lactosyl and S-CH₂ protons), 2.266–2.059 (21H, m, OCOCH₃), 1.615 (3H, q, CH₃), 1.371–1.256 (2H, t, -NH) (Anal. Calcd. for C₄₂H₅₁N₃O₁₈S : C, 54.90; H, 5.88; O, 31.37; N, 4.57; S, 3.48. Found : C, 50.3; H, 5.40; O, 31.23; N, 4.48; S, 3.51%).

When the reaction of hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamide extended to several other aryl isocyanates corresponding 1-hepta-*O*-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-*O*-tolyl-2-*S*-benzyl-isothiobiurets (**3b-i**) have been isolated.

1-Hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-m-tolyl-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3b) :

IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3427 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.), 1750 (C=O str.), 1516 (C=N str.), 1407 (C-N str.), 669 (C=S str.), 926 (char. of lactose unit), 759 (*meta* substituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 7.356–6.609 (11H, m, aromatic and S-CH₂ protons), 5.352–3.5 (14H, m, lactosyl-H), 2.266–2.05 (21H, m, OCOCH₃), 1.627 (3H, q, CH₃), 1.286–1.255 (2H, t, -NH) (Anal. Calcd. for C₄₂H₅₁N₃O₁₈S : C, 54.90; H, 5.88; O, 31.37; N, 4.57; S, 3.48. Found : C, 50.3; H, 5.40; O, 31.23; N, 4.48; S, 3.51%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-p-tolyl-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3c) :

IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3300 (NH str.), 3021 (Ar-H str.), 1750 (C=O str.), 1481 (C=N str.), 1374 (C-N str.), 670 (C=S str.), 927 (char. of lactose unit), 759 (*para* substituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 7.385–7.091 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 5.353–3.602 (16H, m, lactosyl and S-CH₂ protons), 2.376–1.926 (21H, m, OCOCH₃), 1.645 (3H, q, CH₃), 1.253 (2H, t, -NH); ¹³C NMR ν : 171.56 (C=O), 20.7 (OAc), 66.92–77.65 (C of lactose ring), 89.13 (C=S), 130.11–119.29 (Ph-C); Mass : [*m/z*] 917 [M⁺], 812, 619, 559, 503, 478, 331, 263, 169, 109 (Anal. Calcd. for C₄₂H₅₁N₃O₁₈S : C, 54.90; H, 5.88; O, 31.37; N, 4.57; S, 3.48. Found : C, 50.3; H, 5.40; O, 31.23; N, 4.48; S, 3.51%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl- β -D-lactosyl-5-m-chloro-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3d) :

IR (KBr) ν cm⁻¹ : 3432–3683 (NH str.), 3021 (Ar-H str.), 1750 (C=O str.), 1421 (C=N str.), 1373 (C-N str.), 670 (C=S str.), 924 (char. of lactose unit), 761 (*meta* substituted benzene ring); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 7.622–7.0 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 2.374–1.913 (21H, m, -OCOCH₃), 1.254 (2H, d, NH), 5.354–3.675 (14H, m, lactosyl-H); ¹³C NMR δ ppm : 20.92–20.66 (OAc), 77.65–61.16 (carbons of lactosyl ring), 81.88 (C=S), 170.53–169.23 (-C=O, 1C), 130.78–123.51 (aromatic C); Mass : [*m/z*] 937 [M⁺], 875, 478, 367, 331, 169, 109 (Anal. Calcd. for C₄₁H₄₈N₃O₁₈SCl : C, 52.50; H, 5.12; O, 30.73; N, 4.48; S, 3.41; Cl, 3.73. Found : C, 52.46; H, 5.10; O, 30.71; N, 4.43; S, 3.44; Cl, 3.69%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-p-chloro-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3e) :

IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3432–3683 (NH str.), 3021 (Ar-H str.), 1750 (C=O str.), 1421 (C=N str.), 1373 (C-N str.), 670 (C=S str.), 924 (char. of lactose unit), 761 (*para* substituted benzene ring); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 7.459–6.745 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 2.184–2.039 (21H, m, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 1.373–1.256 (2H, t, NH), 5.535–3.603 (14H, m, lactosyl-H) (Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_3\text{O}_{18}\text{SCl}$: C, 52.50; H, 5.12; O, 30.73; N, 4.48; S, 3.41; Cl, 3.73. Found : C, 52.46; H, 5.10; O, 30.71; N, 4.43; S, 3.44; Cl, 3.69%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-o-methoxy-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3f) :

IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3423 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.), 1749 (C=O str.), 1637 (C=N str.), 1407 (C-N str.), 670 (C=S str.), 924 (char. of lactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 8.286–8.261 (2H, t, NH protons), 7.874–7.019 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 2.188–1.612 (21H, m, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 5.354–3.595 (14H, m, lactosyl-H), 6.998–6.850 (2H, t, S- CH_2 protons), 1.612 (3H, q, CH_3); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ δ ppm : 20.97–20.7 (OAc), 77.65–66.93 (carbons of lactosyl ring), 81.88 (C=S), 170.56–170.24 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$, 1C), 129.43–128.90 (aromatic C); Mass : [m/z] 933 [M^+], 914, 897, 812, 559, 360, 331, 169 (Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{51}\text{N}_3\text{O}_{19}\text{S}$: C, 54.01; H, 5.46; O, 32.58; N, 4.50; S, 3.42. Found : C, 53.98; H, 5.41; O, 32.54; N, 4.48; S, 3.44%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-m-methoxy-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3g) :

IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3424 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.), 1749 (C=O str.), 1638 (C=N str.), 1407 (C-N str.), 669 (C=S str.), 926 (char. of lactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 7.355–6.601 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 2.183–2.036 (21H, m, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 5.535–3.768 (14H, m, lactosyl-H), 6.998–6.850 (2H, t, NH), 1.612 (3H, q, CH_3) (Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{51}\text{N}_3\text{O}_{19}\text{S}$: C, 54.01; H, 5.46; O, 32.58; N, 4.50; S, 3.42. Found : C, 53.98; H, 5.41; O, 32.54; N, 4.48; S, 3.44%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-p-methoxy-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3h) :

IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3389 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.), 1749 (C=O str.), 1633 (C=N str.), 1407 (CN str.), 669 (C=S str.), 920 (char. of lactose); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 7.407–6.780 (9H, m, aromatic-H), 2.183–2.034 (21H, m, $-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 1.372–1.284 (2H, t, NH), 5.535–3.602 (16H, m, lactosyl and S- CH_2 protons), 1.636 (3H, q, CH_3) (Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{51}\text{N}_3\text{O}_{19}\text{S}$: C, 54.01; H, 5.46; O, 32.58; N, 4.50; S, 3.42. Found : C, 53.98; H, 5.41; O, 32.54; N, 4.48; S, 3.44%).

1-Hepta-O-acetyl-β-D-lactosyl-5-α-naphthyl-2-S-benzyl-isothiobiurets (3i) :

IR (KBr) ν cm^{-1} : 3452 (NH str.), 3022 (Ar-H str.),

where, Ac = COCH_3 , Bz = $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

R = (a) *o*-Tolyl, (b) *m*-Tolyl, (c) *p*-Tolyl, (d) *m*-Cl-Phenyl, (e) *p*-Cl-Phenyl, (f) *o*-Anisyl, (g) *m*-Anisyl, (h) *p*-Anisyl, (i) 1-Naphthyl

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physicochemical and analytical data of compounds (**3a-i**)

Sr. No.	Product (3a-i)	Reactants (2a-i)	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	[α] _D ³² (0.1, in CHCl ₃)	Found (Required)		<i>R_f</i> (Pet. ether : EtOAc) (1 : 1)	
1.	3a	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	92	209	-	4.57	3.48	0.65	0.65
					128.3	(4.56)	(3.54)		
2.	3b	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	78	210	+65.1	4.57	3.48	0.42	
						(4.54)	(3.51)		
3.	3c	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	91	212	-117	4.57	3.48	0.54	
						(4.48)	(3.51)		
4.	3d	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	86	206	+132	4.47	3.41	0.67	
						(4.44)	(3.44)		
5.	3e	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	77	173	+154	4.47	3.41	0.74	
						(4.44)	(3.48)		
6.	3f	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	90	224	-	4.49	3.42	0.89	
					54.3	(4.45)	(3.47)		
7.	3g	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	84	208	+169	4.49	3.42	0.58	
						(4.46)	(3.44)		
8.	3h	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	91	214	+134	4.49	3.42	0.82	
						(4.46)	(3.46)		
9.	3i	α -Naphthyl	86	215	+97	4.40	3.35	0.84	
						(4.39)	(3.39)		

1750 (C=O str.), 1430 (C=N str.), 671 (C=S str.), 757 (*para* substituted benzene ring), 922 (char. of lactose unit); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 7.8–7.2 (12H, m, aromatic-H), 2.188–1.964 (17H, m, -OCOCH₃), 8.056–8.033 (1H, s, NH), 1.253 (1H, s, NH), 5.469–3.689 (14H, m, lactosyl-H); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) ppm : 170.23 (-C=O), 77.66–70.85 (carbons of lactose ring), 20.47

(-COCH₃); Mass : [*m/z*] 953 [M⁺], 812, 619, 559, 331, 169 (Anal. Calcd. for C₄₆H₅₁N₃O₁₈S : C, 57.92; H, 5.35; O, 30.22; N, 4.40; S, 3.35. Found : C, 57.90; H, 5.32; O, 30.21; N, 4.36; S, 3.38%).

Antimicrobial activity :

Newly synthesized isothiobiurets were tested against following pathogenic microbes for their antibacterial and

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of compounds (**3a-i**)

Compd.	Inhibition zone diameter (mm)						
	Bacteria					Fungi	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
3a	18	15	20	12	16	21	17
3b	20	13	12	16	18	20	19
3c	16	15	15	17	18	19	16
3d	19	18	16	14	19	18	20
3e	22	17	14	18	16	15	19
3f	25	21	13	17	13	20	18
3g	16	14	15	14	19	18	20
3h	18	13	16	17	19	19	17
3i	-	11	13	-	11	16	15
Gentamycine	25	25	25	25	25	-	-
Nystatin	-	-	-	-	-	23	23

antifungal activities using cup plate agar diffusion method²⁵ like *Escheria coli*, *Staphalococcus aureus*, *Psudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Bacillus cereus* and *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* in potato dextrose agar medium. The results of antimicrobial activities are also presented in Table 2.

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